

Identification of the damage and failure mechanisms of a 3D carbon-carbon composite under uniaxial loading

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SUMMARY: We identify the damage and failure modes of a 3D carbon-carbon composite loaded in tension along its orthotropy axis z , through the analysis of a series of experiments (e.g. Scanning Electron and Optical Microscopy). We establish that its ultimate strength is mainly due to the z -axis yarns which were not damaged (or little damaged) by specimen machining. The evaluation of the failure strength and the corresponding standard deviation are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: 3D carbon-carbon composites, damage and failure mechanisms, uniaxial tensile tests, brittle materials, probabilistic approach.

INTRODUCTION

Several industrial equipments, for example in aeronautics, civil or military nuclear applications, imply multiaxially loaded brittle materials for which reliable failure models are necessary. Our final aim is to propose a methodology of elaboration and validation of such models that uses a probabilistic approach. In order to keep our study close to practice, we selected a 3D carbon-carbon composite that is submitted to triaxial tensile strains along its orthotropy axes. The first step to elaborate a failure criterion consists in determining the local causes of damage and failure, and also to quantify the scatter of the failure strength. Several uniaxial tensile tests were therefore carried out along one yarn direction (z -axis).

DESCRIPTION OF THE MATERIAL

The composite is made of PAN-based carbon yarns arranged along three orthogonal directions, x , y and z , each yarn being composed of thousands of continuous fibers. The textile architecture is impregnated under high temperature and pressure conditions with a carbon matrix obtained from petroleum pitch. The composite can be considered periodic, and the smallest elementary cell that can describe its mechanical behavior is given in Fig. 1. Assuming its geometry is perfect, the material is orthotropic at the macroscopic scale. x , y and z are its orthotropy axes (with x equivalent to y).

Fig. 1: Elementary cell of a 3D carbon-carbon composite; a matrix octet represents an eighth of the elementary cell and is made of matrix; the z-axis yarns have a square section whereas the x- and y-axis yarns are identical and have a rectangular-shaped section.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composite is loaded under uniaxial tension along its orthotropy axis z by an MTS servo-hydraulic machine. Each end of the specimen is gripped to the machine via a flexible Cardan joint [1] in order to eliminate the possible geometrical defects of the specimen or the assembly misalignments. Cyclic displacements are prescribed at $\pm 0,05$ mm/s.

Fig. 2: Geometry of the uniaxial tensile specimen.

The specimen geometry is presented in Fig. 2. Its ends are cone-shaped to ensure a uniform distribution of the load. Its gauge section is a square and measures 4,8 mm x 4,8 mm which is equivalent to 3 x 3 elementary cells. However the section is not symmetric with respect to x and y, and specimens containing only 4 or 6 intact z-axis yarns have been tested (Fig. 3). Each specimen is equipped with four strain gauges glued on one face, in the same cross-section located in the middle of the gauge length (Fig. 2).

Fig. 3: Cross-section of the six specimens: they possess only 4 or 6 z-axis yarns which were not partially cut into by machining. The yarns that are cut into less than 50% of their original cross-sectional area are boxed (---).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A damage and failure scenario for specimen A1

The progress of the test on specimen A1 is analyzed. At 3240 N, the specimen emits a sound and simultaneously a sudden decrease of the strain ϵ_1 given by gauge 1 is observed while the load F remains constant (Fig. 4). The other measures ϵ_2 , ϵ_3 and ϵ_4 are not affected. A local phenomenon has occurred: it corresponds to the failure of the most cut into z-axis yarns, located under gauge 1. When these yarns break, the load they carried is redistributed to the remainder of the material: F does not decrease, whereas the local strain ϵ_1 , which was an image of their elongation, decreases. The same phenomenon occurs at 3595 N: the strains ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 suddenly decrease at an almost constant load level. It can be attributed to the failure of the z-axis yarns located under gauge 2. For a load level of 3646 N, the specimen fails.

Fig. 4: Load F versus strains $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_3$ and ϵ_4 measured by the four gauges 1, 2, 3 and 4, for specimen A1. The arrows indicate the loading direction.

To propose a more accurate damage and failure scenario, some postmortem analyses were carried out. A sample polished in a (xOy) plane shows that there is a weak cohesion between z -axis yarns and the transverse part (matrix and x - and y -axis yarns) (Fig. 5). This fact has also been observed before any mechanical loading. We assume that crack initiation occurs in the transverse part, along an interface between yarn and matrix, and that it propagates in mode I, perpendicularly to the z -axis. Robinson et al. [2] have observed the same phenomenon for a composite whose architecture and precursors are analogous to the one studied herein. During its propagation, the crack will not damage the z -axis yarns carrying the load because of the

weakness of the interface. Besides a sample polished in a (xOz) plane shows the presence of cracks in the transverse part extending over several centimeters: it is partially presented in Fig. 5. It means that the transverse part has significantly degraded before the failure of the specimen. We consider that the transverse part has a very small contribution (if any) to the failure strength of the specimen, contrary to the z -axis yarns.

Fig. 5: Observations, by Optical Microscopy, of samples polished in (xOy) and (xOz) planes.

The observation of the fractured surface by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) shows the failure mechanism of each yarn (Fig. 6). In the case of unidirectional carbon-carbon composites, Zaldivar et al. [3] attribute an uneven fracture profile to a failure mode dominated by the fibers. This profile is also observed for each z -axis yarn of specimen A1, allowing us to assume a fiber-dominated failure mode. It means that during loading, the interstitial matrix of a z -axis yarn degrades without damaging fibers, because of a weak interface. The fibers finally break at their weakest point, which has a random location along the z -axis, leading to an uneven failure profile. This mechanism has also been observed at the specimen scale, between the z -axis yarns and the transverse part. Additionally, each broken yarn has a different profile: we consider that there is no interaction between them when they fail. Only side effects have been noticed, the peripheral yarns being more pulled out than those in the middle.

Fig. 6: Failure surface of specimen A1.

The damage and failure scenario for specimen A1 can finally be summarized as follows: during the test, the transverse part progressively cracks, until z-axis yarns mainly contribute to the resistance. Simultaneously, the interstitial matrix damages inside each yarn, until the fibers mainly resist. Then comes a first critical load at which the most cut into z-axis yarns fail, i.e. those located under gauge 1. Then the z-axis yarns located under gauge 2 break. All the other yarns fail later.

Comparison between the failure strengths of the six samples

Fig. 7: Load F versus average strain ϵ_{av} measured by the gauges, for specimen A1. When the z-axis yarns under gauge 1 have failed, ϵ_{av} is the average of ϵ_2 , ϵ_3 and ϵ_4 . When the z-axis yarns under gauge 2 have failed, ϵ_{av} is the average of ϵ_3 and ϵ_4 .

Poss [4] establishes that a composite having an architecture analogous to the one studied herein has a brittle behavior in tension along its orthotropy axes. When not considering the early failure of some yarns, our tests give similar results (Fig. 7). Besides a brittle material is sensitive to its imperfections and classically exhibits a scatter of its failure load: we have therefore decided to evaluate it for the six samples. But the proportion and space distribution of z-axis yarns varies from one specimen to the other (Fig. 3), and a failure load F_R corresponds to an amount of resisting z-axis yarns which is different for each test. The failure loads cannot be directly compared, yet the failure strength σ_F , defined as the ratio between F_R and the resisting section can. The resisting section is the sum of the areas of the z-axis yarns that contribute to the failure strength: its exact determination requires the following analysis.

The six specimens possess either 6 or 12 cut into z-axis yarns (Fig. 3), the area of each being a fraction of an intact yarn. For one specimen, the resisting section can be evaluated as the contribution of the intact z-axis yarns and an amount of cut into ones, which all have a different surface. The example of the calculation of σ_F as a function of the percentage of cut into surface is given in Fig. 8 for specimen A2. Taking into account more and more cut into z-axis yarns for the evaluation of the resisting section (or of σ_F) increases discretely the amount of cut into surface from 0 to 100 %, and therefore reduces the value of σ_F .

Fig. 8: Failure strength versus percentage of cut into surface considered for the evaluation of that failure strength, for specimen A2: the z-axis yarns taken into account are boxed (- - -).

We now have to determine which value of the resisting section is the most appropriate in the evaluation of σ_F . Figure 9 shows the average failure strength for the six tests and its

coefficient of variation (i.e. the ratio of the non-biased standard deviation to the average failure strength) as functions of the percentage of cut into surface. It clearly reveals that the smallest coefficient of variation is obtained when considering the z-axis yarns cut into less than 50%. For higher percentages, the coefficient remains almost constant, and the average σ_F is nearly unchanged, compared to lower percentages. The contribution of more than 50% cut into yarns is negligible, their cross-section being small. On the example of specimen A1, considering 50% of cut into surface allows not to take into account the z-axis yarns that fail prematurely (Fig.3). We then recommend defining σ_F as the ratio of the measured failure load to the sum of the areas of the z-axis yarns cut into less than 50%.

Fig. 9: Average failure strength for the six tests and its associated coefficient of variation versus the percentage of cut into surface of z-axis yarns.

Additionally we compared that definition to some more conventional ones. The coefficient of variation for four possible evaluations of σ_F is plotted in Fig. 10: the smallest one is obtained when considering the z-axis yarns cut into less than 50%. Otherwise, when are considered the global section, all the z-axis yarns or only the intact ones, the coefficient of variation is equal

to 14%, 15% and 9% respectively, i.e. higher than the value found previously. The difference between the first two values (14% and 15%) is due to the fact that the area of all the z-axis yarns varies from one test to the other, whereas the global section always remains the same.

Fig. 10: Comparison of the coefficient of variation for four methods of evaluation of σ_F :
 1- (F_R / global section measuring 4,8 mm x 4,8 mm);
 2 - (F_R / section of all the z-axis yarns); 3- (F_R / section of the intact z-axis yarns);
 4- (F_R / section of z-axis yarns cut into less than 50%).

The definition we propose leads to an average failure strength of 935 MPa \pm 61 MPa and is representative of the behavior of the yarns, i.e. of a mesoscale behavior. Rémond [5] carried out tensile experiments on yarns extracted from a composite analogous to the one studied herein. The failure strength was found to be equal to 968 MPa, which is into the range of our mesoscale evaluation. The fact that our average strength is smaller than the one evaluated by Rémond may be linked to the processing of the composite. Moreover a larger number of experiments should be taken into account for σ_F (and its scatter) to be better representative of the material. Lastly, since the z-axis yarns represent a surface fraction of 25% along the z-direction, a value of 234 MPa \pm 15 MPa is found for the failure strength at the macroscopic scale.

CONCLUSIONS

We have established that the resistance of the composite in tension along its orthotropy axis z is mainly due to the intact and little cut into z-axis yarns. In such conditions, the failure strength is defined by taking only into account the intact z-axis yarns and those which are cut into less than 50%. For the six tests, it leads to the smallest scatter of the failure strength, and the contribution of more damaged yarns to the failure strength is very limited. By using this type of analysis, the scatter due to geometric differences can be avoided and it is believed that the remaining scatter is related to material properties.

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